

MAGNESIUM FOR INDIVIDUALS WHO PRACTICE SPORTS ACTIVITIES

Irakli Chaganava^{1,2} - Associate Professor, PhD in chemistry;

Email: chaganava@irakli.info

¹Georgian State Teaching University of Physical Education and Sport. Tbilisi, Georgia.

²Institute of Cybernetics of Georgian Technical University. Tbilisi, Georgia.

Keywords: sports, magnesium, training, micronutrients, metabolism, health, endurance, fatigue, recovery.

Introduction. Regular exercise and an adequate diet are fundamental to achieving optimal athletic performance. Macronutrients and micronutrients are an important component of proper nutrition for an athlete. Magnesium and zinc contribute to the accumulation of muscle mass and the maintenance of cardiorespiratory function [1]. Magnesium is essential for the activity of more than 700 proteins in the human proteome. During physical exertion, potassium, sodium, calcium and magnesium provide cycles of contraction-relaxation of the heart and muscles, as well as the implementation of oxidative phosphorylation during the biosynthesis of ATP. Magnesium is necessary for the regulation of neuromuscular conduction, heart rhythm, vascular tone, immunity, blood glucose levels, and the balance of decay-reconstruction of connective tissue (ligaments, cartilage, bones) [2]. Studies conducted in different countries have shown a widespread prevalence of magnesium deficiency in population samples. A reduced supply of magnesium (plasma magnesium levels <0.80 mmol/L) contributes to an increased risk of seizures, cardiac arrhythmias, hypertension, mitral valve prolapse, sleep disorders, maladjustment, etc.

Objectives. The research task is a substantiated assessment of the importance of providing athletes with magnesium, taking into account such functions of magnesium as energy, endocrinological and neuronal. The widespread prevalence of low magnesium supply makes it necessary to take special measures to compensate for magnesium deficiency: changes in diet, taking special magnesium preparations, etc. Prevention of magnesium deficiency in athletes is especially important.

Materials and methods. This work is based on experimental observations of the level of magnesium in various biosubstrates during intense physical activity. The objects of monitoring were such biological materials as plasma and blood serum, including erythrocytes; in some cases, the level of magnesium in urine and in sweat was observed. Serum electrolyte levels were measured in trained, experienced long-distance runners (n=18) before and after a standard 42 km marathon, during which they did not consume any electrolyte solution. Also, observations of professional swimmers were carried out. Recall that swimming is a special kind of sport that requires the maintenance of body temperature in the water; magnesium is involved in thermoregulation of the body. Additionally, work was carried out to identify the difference in physiological processes between athletes and untrained healthy individuals. The physical activity of the latter was carried out on treadmills. The study consistently examines the dynamics of magnesium levels during exercise, the relationship between magnesium and maximum aerobic capacity, hormonal balance, and cardiovascular health of athletes. The relationship between magnesium supply and metabolic parameters during physical exertion, endurance, recovery after exertion, including indicators of immunity, is revealed. The results of studies of the use of organic magnesium salts in athletes are considered.

Results and discussions. Concentrations of magnesium in blood plasma and erythrocytes are maintained physiologically within certain ranges of values due to the regulation of magnesium adsorption in the small intestine and reabsorption in the kidneys. The results of the studies cited below show that a typical result of intense exercise is a decrease in plasma/serum blood levels; in some studies, a decrease in magnesium levels in both plasma and erythrocytes has been noted [3]. The marathon runners (n=24) showed a significant decrease in blood and urine magnesium levels by the end of the race. Serum iron concentration increased significantly, and magnesium levels decreased significantly in both serum and urine. Measurements of the loss of sodium, potassium, calcium and magnesium with sweat during a 10 km run (running time 41 ± 10 min) showed that body weight loss averaged 1.45 kg. For each kilogram of weight loss, the loss of calcium through the skin was 20 mg, potassium - 200 mg, sodium - 800 mg, and magnesium - only 5 mg. With prolonged swimming, the level of magnesium in the blood plasma decreases even in well-trained swimmers (n=8): by 12% after 2 minutes of exercise and by 21% after 30 minutes. At the same time, the levels of magnesium in erythrocytes and urine did not change significantly [4]. The degree to which magnesium levels are reduced depends on the intensity of the exercise. In professional handball players (n=14) during training and competition, the levels of Mg^{2+} were associated with the volume of the load [5] (Fig. 1). The volume of loads was assessed by the "residual" heart rate: for each athlete, the percentage of training time was calculated during which the athlete's heart rate increased by more than 80% of the resting heart rate. Thus, during intense physical exertion, the body loses magnesium, which is reflected in a decrease in magnesium concentrations in the studied bio-substrates. However, transient renal failure (occurring, for example, during long-distance running) can lead to an increase in plasma magnesium levels. In amateur athletes (n=7), plasma levels of Mg^{2+} significantly increased after a 100 km run. At the same time, no significant changes in the concentration of magnesium in erythrocytes were observed. At the same time, the levels of creatinine in the blood plasma significantly increased, which indicates a deterioration in renal function. A positive correlation was found between the levels of magnesium and creatinine in blood plasma. Apparently, in the studied group there were athletes in whom running a long distance led to a breakdown of the countercurrent-multiplying system of the kidneys.

Fig. 1. Correlation between training volume and plasma and red blood cell magnesium levels in handball players. [5]

According to the conclusions carried out by different groups of researchers, the selection of the pharmacological form of the drug, (formulas of magnesium-containing active substances) plays a very important role. The variety of marketed magnesium preparations is based primarily on their pharmacokinetics and then on their pharmacodynamics. Certain groups of the magnesium form target primarily specific organs or their systems. Thus, **Table 1** summarizes the characteristics of some forms of magnesium preparations.

DRUG FORM	$\omega(\text{Mg})$	FEATURES
Magnesium oxide	40%	The lowest level of bioavailability, but the highest concentration of Mg. It is advisable for acute deficiency. Has the least selectivity.
Magnesium citrate	11%	The highest rate of absorption by the body. Appropriate for quickly obtaining the beneficial effects of magnesium.
Magnesium malate	15%	Quite a high degree of absorption. A good option for muscle pain, helps with fatigue.
Magnesium glycinate	14%	Has a pronounced calming effect. Glycine is an inhibitory neurotransmitter and can enhance the relaxing effect of magnesium. It is a suitable form of Mg for psycho-emotional relief.
Magnesium amino acid chelates	<6%	Has the highest level of bioavailability (90-95%). This form is best suited in cases where additional amino acid production is required.
Magnesium taurate	9%	Magnesium taurate relaxes the heart muscle, improves blood circulation in the vessels. This is a suitable magnesium supplement option for people with high blood pressure and heart problems.
Magnesium Orotate	7%	It can be used to treat extracellular magnesium deficiency. Improves regeneration processes, stimulates the synthesis of myocardial contractile proteins, promotes cellular utilization of magnesium and the manifestation of its effects.
Magnesium sulfate	20%	It is advisable to use for absorption through the skin (taking mineral baths). It helps to quickly replenish Mg deficiency, lower blood pressure, relax muscles, smooth out stress, relieve pain, relieve muscle cramps.
Magnesium chloride	25%	In second place in terms of magnesium concentration after oxide. It is used mainly as a remedy for external use, it is produced in the form of gels, soaps, oils, lotions. Helps with muscle cramps.
Magnesium L-threonate	15%	A relatively new form of magnesium on the market has only been studied recently. Able to pass the blood-brain barrier. It has a positive effect on improving cognitive abilities, in particular short-term and long-term memory. Improves sleep quality.

Table 1. Summary of approved magnesium-containing preparations and their features.

Conclusions. Magnesium is not the only element that is important for athletes. For example, zinc is involved in the regulation of leptin levels and is a lipid mobilizing factor [6]. Research confirms that magnesium is characterized by a certain range of biological functions that are fundamentally important for maintaining an athlete in good physiological shape. Particularly noteworthy are such functions of magnesium as (1) the implementation of the biological functions of adrenaline, insulin, and a number of other hormones, (2) neuronal signal transmission (NMDA receptors, catecholamine receptors), (3) energy metabolism (enzymes of glycolysis and the Krebs cycle). Clinical studies confirm the fundamental importance of magnesium supply for the most effective "tuning" of the athlete's body.

In certain cases, the selection of the pharmacological form of the drug is essential. Since magnesium-containing substances have different target physiological systems and bioavailability characteristics.

References

1. Lukaski H.C. Magnesium, zinc, and chromium nutrition and athletic performance // *Can J Appl Physiol.* 2001. Vol. 26 (Suppl). P. 13–22.
2. Volpe S.L. Magnesium and the Athlete // *Curr Sports Med Rep.* 2015. Vol. 14. P. 279–283.
3. Rayssiguier Y., Guezennec C.Y., Durlach J. New experimental and clinical data on the relationship between magnesium and sport // *Magnes Res.* 1990. Vol. 3 (2). P. 93–102.
4. Laires M.J., Alves F. Changes in plasma, erythrocyte, and urinary magnesium with prolonged swimming exercise // *Magnes Res.* 1991. Vol. 4 (2). P. 119–122.
5. Громова О.А., Егорова Е.Ю., Торшин И.Ю., Громов А.Н., Гоголева И.В. О роли магния в спортивной медицине // *РМЖ.* 2016. № 1. С. 1–1.
6. Zhao J., Fan B., Wu Z. et al. Serum zinc is associated with plasma leptin and Cu-Zn SOD in elite male basketball athletes // *J Trace Elem Med Biol.* 2015. Vol. 30. P. 49–53.